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**Project Process Management Bridge between Project and
Information Technology**

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In the current scenario, Advanced Technologies and technological means are easily available that can effectively build the gap between project processes and the information technology environment. The objective of this study is to imply the repetitive activities performed in the context of an organization's normal, everyday operations. This research was conducted on the basis of detailed literature review. Validation of the model system was done through interviews of the people involved in project management and experts in Information Technology. The findings of the research shows that new technologies integrate project processes with information technology service to provide an enterprise-wide view of the organization's project processes mapped to the information technology infrastructure. Information technology and line of business owners can share this view, providing a common language with which to communicate and collaborate. Technologies are now available that bridge the gap between project processes and the information technology environment. This convergence requires that both parties understand the relationships between project and information technology resources that support these services and processes.

Keywords: Project Management; Business Organization;
Project Process; Information Technology